

Hetero-ring Formations with Thiocarbohydrazide.

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In a previous paper, it has been shown that dithio-*p*-urazine can be prepared from thiocarbohydrazide by the action of potassium ethyl xanthate and it has also been suggested there that the compound $C_2H_4N_4S_2$ of Purgotti and Vigano, (*Gazzetta*, 1901, 31, ii, 563) which they regarded as dithio-*p*-urazine was probably a thiodiazole compound (*Trans.*, 1924, 125, 1215). Arndt and Bielich (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 809) by repeating the experiment of Purgotti and Vigano, could not get the so-called dithio-*p*-urazine of Purgotti, and obtained a compound of the same composition but differing in properties and ascribed to the new compound the formula of N-4-amino-dithio-urazole.

Two more improved methods have now been discovered for the preparation of dithio-*p*-urazine. For the desired synthesis, the use of thiocarbohydrazide has been dispensed with and it has been achieved by allowing hydrazine hydrate to react directly with carbondisulphide. The mechanism of the reaction is as follows :

That the above scheme of reaction is correct, has been proved by synthesising dithio-*p*-urazine from thiocarbohydrazide and carbondisulphide.

Potassium ethyl xanthate yields dithio-*p*-urazine by reacting with hydrazine hydrate much more easily (*vide* expt.). Potassium-dithiocarbazinate formed by the action of hydrazine and potassium ethyl xanthate, reacting with another molecule of the same substance and with the elimination of two molecules of potassium hydrosulphide produces one molecule of dithio-*p*-urazine, thus :

Dithio-*p*-urazine has been desulphurised by treatment with mercuric oxide yielding *p*-urazine. The above reaction lends additional support to the dithio-*p*-urazine structure for our compound.

One molecule of potassium sulphocyanide reacts with one molecule of thiocarbonylhydrazide yielding mainly thiocarbonylhydrazido-thiocarbonamide.

Besides this, there is also formed a very small quantity of a light yellow-coloured substance which could not be further studied for want of sufficient quantity of this material.

The closure of the ring of the above thiocarbonylhydrazido-thiocarbonamide has been effected with the aid of strong hydrochloric acid, when the thio-compound loses one molecule of ammonia with the formation of the hydrochloride of N-4-aminodithiourazole of Arndt and Bielich, from which the free base can be easily liberated by sodium acetate. The identity of this compound with that of

Arndt and Bielich has been established by preparing the benzal derivative, the dibenzylthio-ether and the disulphide; all of them melting at the same temperature as the corresponding derivatives of Arndt and Bielich compound.

The behaviour of potassium cyanate towards thiocarbohydrazide has also been studied and it has been found that the reaction proceeds exactly in a similar fashion as in the case of potassium sulphocyanide; the resulting thiocarbohydrazido-carbonamide, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CONH}_2$, in its turn, gives *N*-4-amino-monothiourazole:

(Compare Freund and Imgart, Ber, 28, 946.) The presence of one mercaptanic group and the hydrazine residue in the compound is proved by the fact that it gives a disulphide with iodine and a monobenzal-derivative with benzaldehyde.

Phenyl isocyanate differs in its behaviour towards thio-carbohydrazide from potassium cyanate and thiocyanate in the sense that both of the hadrazino groups are attacked by the reagent yielding *s*-di-phenylcarbonamido-thiocarbohydrazide, thus:

Stolle and Bowles (Ber., 41, 1101) obtained 1-amino-5-thiol-2-hydrazino-1:3:4-triazole by long and continued heating of a mixture of hydrazine hydrate and thiocarbohydrazide. If instead of the free basic compounds, an intimate mixture of their hydrochlorides are heated to 170-180°, the reaction takes an entirely different course

and there is formed 5-thio-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-isotetrazole, thus:

As thiocarbamide reacts with monochloroacetic acid to form pseudo-thiohydantoin, thiocarbonylhydrazide reacting in the pseudo form, gives a similar compound with monochloroacetic ester, thus:

2-Hydrazino-5-Keto-2, 3, 4, 5 tetrahydro-1, 3, 4 thiodiazine. The resulting compound gives a benzal derivative with benzaldehyde and possesses no mercaptanic properties.

The action of glyoxal on thiocarbo-hydrazide has been found to be very interesting, in as much as, a hepta-tetrazine compound is formed by the elimination of two molecules of water from molecular quantities of the reacting materials:

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Dithio-p-urazine.

(a) A mixture of thiocarbonylhydrazide and carbonyl disulphide in molecular proportions was heated in presence of water in a sealed tube at 130-140° for three to four hours. After cooling white crystalline deposits were found in the

tube which were taken out and separated by filtration from the mother liquor. The solid residue was then dissolved in hot water and boiled with animal charcoal to remove the tarry matter and filtered hot. The filtrate on concentration yielded the dithio-*p*-urazine. It was recrystallised from hot water with the addition of a few drops of concentrated HCl in white rectangular plates melting at 203-204° with decomposition. The yield is almost theoretical.

(b) When a mixture of hydrazine hydrate (one molecule) and carbon disulphide (two molecules) was heated in presence of water in a sealed tube at 100° for 5-6 hours, little or no reaction took place. On raising the temperature to 140-150° the reaction came to an end in the course of 2-3 hours. The solid residue was then treated in the same way as described in (a). The yield in this case also was fairly good.

(c) A mixture of hydrazine hydrate (one molecule), alcoholic potassium hydroxide (one molecule) and carbon disulphide (two mols.) was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for four to five hours. The light brownish black solution was filtered. The filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl and again filtered and was then boiled with a small quantity of animal charcoal. The filtrate on concentration or better on the addition of a few drops of concentrated HCl, deposited white crystals of dithio-*p*-urazine. The dithio-*p*-urazine prepared according to all the above methods gave the same dibenzyl-ether (m. p. 142° C; S=19.53), the same disulphide (m. p. 218° C with decomp.; S=43.94) as described in our previous paper (Trans., 1924, 125, 1215).

Thiocarbohydrazido-thiocarbonamide.

An aqueous solution of one molecule of thiocarbonylhydrazide hydrochloride and two molecules of potassium

sulphocyanide was boiled for five hours in a flask fitted with an upright condenser. The contents of the flask while hot contained a very small quantity of a light yellow crystalline mass. The filtered solution on standing for several hours, deposited thiocarbonyldrazido-thiocarbonamide in long white needles and was recrystallised from hot water; it melted at 218-219°C.

Found: N=42.38; S=38.91 per cent.

$C_2H_7N_2S_2$ requires N=42.42; S=38.78 per cent.

N-4-Amino-dithiourazole.

When thiocarbonyldrazido-thiocarbonamide was heated with a few c.c.'s of strong hydrochloric acid for ten to fifteen minutes, it was converted into the hydrochloride of N-4-amino-dithiourazole. The excess of hydrochloric acid was removed by evaporation on the water bath and the remaining solution was then treated with an excess of sodium acetate solution when the free base separated out. It was then purified by crystallising from water acidified with a drop or two of hydrochloric acid. It melted at 228° with decomposition. It was readily soluble in hot water, difficultly in alcohol and insoluble in all other organic solvents.

Found: N=38.2; S=43.19 per cent.

$C_2H_4N_2S_2$ requires N=37.9; S=43.24 per cent.

The compound thus prepared gave the same benzal derivative with benzaldehyde (m. p. 136°), the same dibenzyl-thioether (m. p. 147°) and the disulphide (m. p. 214° with decomposition) as the corresponding derivatives of Arndt and Bielich's N-4-amino-dithiourazole (*ibid*).

Thiocarbonyldrazido-carbonamide.

To a solution of one molecule of thiocarbonyldrazide hydrochloride was gradually added an aqueous solution of two mols. of potassium cyanate under cooling. The reaction commenced at once. The mixture was allowed

to stand for an hour and then filtered. The solid mass thus obtained, crystallised from hot water in white rectangular plates melting at 230°. The yield was extremely poor.

Found: N = 47.02; S = 21.58 per cent.

$C_8H_7ON_2S$ requires N = 46.97; S = 21.47 per cent.

N-4-Amino-thiourazole.

When thiocarbohydrazo-carbonamide was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid for about twenty minutes, it was converted into the hydrochloride of N-4-amino-thiourazole. The solution was then treated with an excess of sodium acetate solution when the free base was liberated. It was then crystallised from water containing a little hydrochloric acid, in white needles melting at 195-196° with decomposition. It is both basic and acidic in nature.

Found: N = 42.45 per cent.

$C_8H_7ON_2S$ requires N = 42.42 per cent.

The *benzal* derivative was obtained by following the same method as described in the preparation of the benzal derivative of N-4-amino-dithiourazole. It was crystallised from benzene in white needles melting at 150-151°.

Found: S = 14.45 per cent.

$C_8H_7ON_2S$ requires S = 14.54 per cent.

The *disulphide* was prepared in the same way as in the preparation of the corresponding derivative of N-4-amino-dithiourazole. It melted at 180-181°C with decomposition. Found: S = 24.76 per cent; $C_{12}H_{11}ON_2S_2$ requires S = 24.61 per cent.

Thiocarbohydrazido-dicarbonyldiphenylamide.

On mixing an aqueous solution, or better, a dilute hydrochloric acid solution of one molecule of thiocarbohydrazide and two molecules of phenyl isocyanate at

the ordinary temperature, the diphenyl-dicarbonamide derivative separated in white plates. It was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution, precipitated with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from a large quantity of boiling water. It melted at 216-217°C. Found: N=24.46 per cent. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires N=24.42 per cent.

5-Thio-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-isotetrazole.

An intimate mixture of the hydrochlorides of thiocarbohydrazide and hydrazine in molecular proportions was heated in an oil-bath at a temperature between 170-180°C for three to four hours, with frequent stirring when a semi-solid molten mass was formed which, however, solidified on cooling. The powdered mass was then extracted with glacial acetic acid and precipitated from the solution by the addition of water, as a light yellow amorphous powder, melting at 126-127°C. Found: N=55.41 per cent. CH_4N_4S requires N=53.84 per cent. From six gms. of thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride only 0.35 gm. of the resulting product could be obtained in a pure condition.

Thiocarbohydrazide and monochloroacetic ester: Formation of 2-hydrazino-5-keto-2, 3, 4, 5-tetrahydro-1, 3, 4-thiodiazine.

An alcoholic solution of one mol. of monochloroacetic ester was gradually added to an alcoholic solution of thiocarbohydrazide (1 mol.) and potassium hydroxide (1 mol.), when the reaction commenced with evolution of heat and separation of a white crystalline product. After standing for about half an hour, the crystalline mass was separated by filtration and crystallised from a large quantity of water in white plates, which melted with decomposition at 220°C. Found: S=22.06 per cent. $C_8H_8ON_4S$ requires S=21.92 per cent.

The *benzal* derivative was prepared by shaking a hydrochloric acid solution of the substance with benzaldehyde when a white solid mass gradually separated. It was then crystallised from alcohol in white plates melting at 149-150°C. Found: S=13·89; $C_{10}H_{10}ON_4S$ requires S=13·67 per cent.

Thiocarbohydrazide and Glyoxal: Formation of a heptatetrazine compound.

An aqueous solution of one mol. of thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride was boiled with one mol. of glyoxal-sodium bisulphite. The solution assumed a light brown colour and a brownish yellow precipitate was gradually formed. The heating was continued for three to four hours. After separating the solid mass by filtration, it was purified by dissolving in caustic soda solution and precipitating with hydrochloric acid. It was then crystallised from pyridine. The light brownish yellow crystalline compound thus obtained, melted at 220°C with decomposition. Found: N=43·11; S=24·80 per cent. $C_3H_4N_4S$ requires N=43·75, S=24·80 per cent.

The action of other di-aldehydes, di-ketones and diamines upon thiocarbohydrazide is under investigation and will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

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